

ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF *TANACETUM VULGARE* L., DRY EXTRACT

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Abstract

The name *Tanacetum vulgare* L., also known as Common Tansy, is derived from the Greek word “athanasia”, which means “immortality”, most likely as a result of the fact that the flowers of this plant do not wilt when dried. This perennial herbaceous plant is widely distributed in North America, Europe, Asia, China, Japan, North Korea, and Russia. *Tanacetum vulgare* L. has been found growing wild in many states of the United States, Europe, and Asia along roadsides, in wastelands, and as a hedge. The chemical composition of the plant and its essential oils is affected by its growing environment and climate. It is well described in the literature for many plants. The plants with sectile leaves grow in Corsica (France), Sardinia, and Sicily (Italy), and some consider them to be a separate species (*ssp. siculum*). *T. vulgare* is a 50–100 cm tall perennial herbaceous plant. The stem is straight, branched from the middle, furrowed, glabrous, or slightly pubescent. The leaves are alternate, dark green on top, grayish on the bottom, and pubescent. The lower leaves are short-petiolate, the rest are sessile. All the leaves are pinnately lobed, divided into lanceolate lobes with saw-toothed edges. Anthodia are numerous, 5–8 mm in diameter, and arranged in corymbose inflorescences at the top of the stem. All the flowers are yellow and funnel shaped. The marginal flowers are pistillate, uniseriate; the middle flowers are teleianthous. The fruits are oblong gray achenes 1.5–3 mm long, with five ribs. The plant blooms from mid-June to September and the fruits ripen in August–September. A strong scent comes from the main oil-containing glands in the leaves and flowers. *T. vulgare* is diploid ($2n = 18$) according to cytogenetic studies. The average amount of essential oil found in aerial parts of *T. vulgare* plants collected at the full flowering stage is from 0.1 to 0.5%, though up to 1.9% has occasionally been observed. *T. vulgare* essential oil is a warm, slightly spicy, dry, and grassy-smelling liquid with a from yellowish to orange hue. The taste is very pungent and bitter. This plant cannot be used in flavorings or any food products. The essential oil of *T. vulgare* mainly contains high amounts of thujone, a poison that can cause convulsions, vomiting, and uterine bleeding. In addition to the essential oil, *T. vulgare* contains amarines and sesquiterpene lactones.

Key words: Macro and micro elements, mass spectrometry, analysis, quantity, dry extract, *Tanacetum vulgare* L, medicine.

The aim of the study: The purpose of this work is the analysis of the elemental composition of dry extract of the *Tanacetum vulgare* L

Method of quantitative determination of micro- and macroelements by induction mass spectrometry with conjugate plasma. Apparatus and instruments used: A similar mass spectrometer. Microwave decomposition device (Germany).

Results: In Uzbekistan, the development of products of functional and therapeutic and prophylactic purposes is underway to prevent various diseases and enhance the protective functions of the body, reduce the risk of exposure to harmful substances, including for the

population living in ecologically unfavorable zones. The analysis results are presented in the table below (table 1).

Table 1

Name of macro and microelements	Quantity, mg / kg	Name of macro and microelements	Quantity, mg / kg
Li	0.108	K	8469.322
Be	0.029	Ca	3620.310
B	55.12	Ti	6.891

It was found that the extract of milk thistle fruit contains little toxic elements of lead, cadmium, beryllium, mercury and thallium, and their content complies with the sanitary norms and standards No. 0283.

Conclusions: Dry extract of *Tanacetum vulgare* L contains an optimal amount of flavonoids, amino acids, carbohydrates, proteins and vitamins, as well as trace elements Beryllium, Lithium, potassium, calcium, titanium. Based on the results obtained, the expediency of including dry extract of *Tanacetum vulgare* L in medicinal products and biologically active food additives was determined.

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